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ANALYSIS OF HEALTH QUALITY INDICATORS IN ROMANIA

Abstract. In healthcare systems, tools and indicators are commonly used as scales to assess the quality of healthcare services and healthcare management activities, thereby evaluating the effectiveness and efficiency of healthcare facilities, public healthcare, and guiding public management. The assessment of healthcare quality in Romania is also increasingly emphasized, with the goal of meeting common European standards. This article analyzes data from Eurostat, the World Health Organization (WHO), and available data sources to evaluate quality indicators in Romania.

Keywords: health indicators, health quality, healthcare management, healthcare systems, Romania.

Introduction. Health is the root of quality of life for every individual and the key to evaluating the performance of each country's healthcare system. Furthermore, healthcare quality significantly impacts other activities, including finance, society,

and technology. Healthcare quality in Romania has improved considerably since the beginning of 2022; However, disparities between regions have created gaps in people's access to healthcare services. This paper uses multidimensional analysis to analyze issues related to healthcare service quality indicators in Romania, including the following main objectives: (1) Analyzing healthcare service quality indicators; (2) Identifying challenges for improving healthcare quality indicators; (3) Proposing improvement methods appropriate to the current context of Romania.

Conceptual framework and Methodology. The Romanian health system operates on core principles specifically set out in Law No. 95/2006 on health reform and related legislation. Based on source documents, the rights and obligations of patients in Romania are mainly regulated in Law No. 46/2003 and are supported by the Romanian Constitution (Lazea & Mureşan, 2015). Healthcare quality in Romania is focused on key quality indicator groups, including demographic indicators, epidemiological indicators, health care service-related indicators, treatment effectiveness and mortality rates, subjective indicators, and patient satisfaction (OECD, 2025). This study conducts a multidimensional analysis of data from existing data sources to assess quality indicators within the Romanian healthcare system.

Root indicators of healthcare quality in Romania. Demographic indicators: Average life expectancy is low, only about 75 years (Balint et al., 2024). However, the infant mortality rate is extremely high in the EU, approximately 5.5 deaths/100,000 live births (OECD, 2025). Romania's aging population increases the risk of healthcare organizations (OECD, 2024). *Epidemiological indicators:* Stroke disease causes the highest death rate, accounting for 35% WHO, 2024). Preventable mortality rates in Romania are high, accounting for 29% of all deaths in Romania. In addition, causes related to ineffective treatment also have a high mortality rate, with 179 deaths/100,000 inhabitants (OECD, 2025). Romania has a much higher mortality rate due to unhealthy lifestyles than the EU, at 62% compared to 44% (Farm, 2021). Indicators related to health services: Hospitalization rates far exceeding outpatient treatment rates and the high cost of outpatient treatment (Lazea & Mureşan, 2015). Uneven distribution of investment and healthcare personnel in Romania leads to inequalities in access to care services between areas (Panaitescu & Andronic, 2022). Romania saw an increase in inpatient beds approximately 728.43 beds in 2023 (Eurostat). In 2023, according to EU health reports, 58,000 cases of measles were recorded, with a fairly high rate of antibiotic resistance associated with more than 500,000 deaths per year (WHO, 2024). Romania allocates less than 2% of its budget to prevention (Balint et al., 2024). Vaccination rates are low; measles vaccination rates for children under one year old are very low, at only about 66%. Treatment outcome indicators show low treatment efficacy; stroke mortality rate is 16.3% (European Commission, 2025). Romania has not prioritized long-term care currently, with only about 6%, and has not provided better support for the elderly and chronically ill patients (Balint et al., 2024). *Subjective indicators:* Patient satisfaction in Romania is low, with 41% of patients rating it as lacking attention and 38% as lacking transparency (OECD, 2025).

Challenges for improving health quality indicators in Romania. Romania's health system exhibits many limitations in health performance due to several reasons, including low average life expectancy, facing numerous problems in managing the public health sector, having an outdated health structure, limited access to primary and specialist care services, and having a relatively high preventable mortality rate. The Romanian health system has poor healthcare performance revealed an urgent need for rethinking and significant investment in equipment, personnel training, and IT infrastructure to improve service quality (Panaitescu & Andronic, 2022).

Measures to improve healthcare performance in Romania. To help Romania improve its performance, the health system needs to implement a synchronized strategy including reforming the technical infrastructure, financial mechanisms and legal framework including establishing a common digital platform at the national level to address the lack of coordination; coordinating existing software solutions into a common system to ensure data interoperability; strengthening IT infrastructure to support big data systems to facilitate rapid clinical decision-making; having policies to mobilize resources and attract large investments; establishing public and private partnerships to finance digitalization initiatives; improving the legal system and active participation of all stakeholders to remove barriers from outdated or overlapping regulations; fully integrating telemedicine into health practice will help the national data system maximize its effectiveness in reducing the burden on health facilities (European Commission, 2025). The development of a health quality measurement toolkit in Romania focuses on four key areas including patient safety, patient experience, human resource training, and clinical effectiveness, based on the needs of the public health system (Ivanković et al., 2024).

Conclusion. Based on the analyzed documents, improving the Romanian healthcare system requires several key solutions, including a patient-centered approach; increased government involvement; mobilization of capital and funding; investment in healthcare infrastructure and equipment; enhancement and support of healthcare resources; digitalization of the system; ensuring equitable access to healthcare; reform of treatment models; improved management capacity; and the development of a specific set of tools for measuring healthcare quality indicators (Panaitescu & Andronic, 2022).

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ETHICS AND GOOD FAITH IN CONTRACTS IN THE DIGITAL AGE AND PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION

Rezumat. Articolul analizează aspecte legate de modul în care digitalizarea fără precedent și dezvoltarea sistemelor de inteligență artificială și utilizarea acestora la încheierea contractelor își pun amprenta principiul bunei-credințe în contracte, consacrat în dreptul contractelor, astfel încât să fie menținut echilibrul contractual. În articol sunt analizate cerințele pentru contracte impuse de utilizarea etică a inteligenței artificiale, pentru a asigura o folosire transparentă și responsabilă a inteligenței artificiale la negocierea, la încheierea și la executarea contractelor. În articol, buna-credință în contracte este analizată în strânsă legătură cu protecția datelor cu caracter personal, conform Regulamentului General privind Protecția Datelor (GDPR). În articol sunt subliniate provocările legate de necesitatea protejării